

Stobbe Reactions with Diethyl Homophthalate. Part I

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The Stobbe condensations of diethyl homophthalate with a few aldehydes and ketones (including cyclic ketones) have been studied. The application of the reaction in the synthesis of some polycyclic compounds has been investigated.

Although the esters of glutaric acid cannot be used in the Stobbe type of condensations, derivatives of glutaric acid have been successfully used by Ruzicka *et al*^{1,7}. Homophthalic acid, which may be regarded as the benzologue of glutaric acid, has also been used in the Stobbe type condensations by Mueller² and Dieckmann³. The potentiality and usefulness of the reaction were explored by Lowenthal and Pappo⁴ by carrying out condensation of homophthalic esters with cyclohexanone, acetone, benzophenone, and benzaldehyde respectively, using sodium hydride as the condensing agent. In all cases they obtained the expected half-esters in excellent yields.

In common with the classical Stobbe condensations with succinic esters (cf. Johnson and Daub⁵), the condensations with homophthalic esters appear to proceed through stabilisation of the intermediate lactones of the type (I) (from benzaldehyde and homophthalic ester) which is irreversibly cleaved by basic catalysts to the half-ester (II). Incidentally, the esters of phenylacetic acid also undergo aldol-type of condensation although the reactivity is much less pronounced.

We have studied the condensations of cinnamic aldehyde and terephthalaldehyde with diethyl homophthalate which lead to the formation of half-esters (III: R=Et) and

1. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, **12**, 1920.
2. *Annalen*, 1831, **491**, 251.
3. *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 1432.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4799.
5. Chatterjea and Mukherjee, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 379.
6. *Idem.*, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 443.
7. "Organic Reactions", Wiley, Vol. VI, p. 1.

(IV: R=Et), respectively. These esters were hydrolysed to the di- and tetracarboxylic acids (III: R=H) and (IV: R=H). Both the acids were reduced with sodium amalgam to the related tetrahydro derivatives, (V) and (VI), respectively. A variety of methods was applied for cyclisation of the acid (V), but in no case was any indication obtained that the cyclisation was taking place as either unchanged product or an intractable tar was obtained probably on account of the unfavourable geometry of the molecule and, hence, the formation of a benzosuberone could be expected. The cyclisation of the tetracarboxylic acid (VI) also did not proceed satisfactorily with hot polyphosphoric acid; a product obtained in poor yield proved to be an indenoisocoumarin^{5,6}. The analytical results support structure (VII) in which one nuclear cyclisation has taken place^{5,6}.

Acetophenone was condensed with diethyl homophthalate in presence of sodium hydride to furnish the crystalline half-ester (VIII) which on cyclisation with acetic anhydride-acetic acid-zinc chloride afforded the keto-ester (IX) (by ester exchange; cf. Johnson and Goldman⁸; Johnson *et al.*⁹). Parallel results were also obtained by employing 1- and 2-acetylnaphthalenes; in each case the indenones were obtained and characterised by preparation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 430.

9. *Ibid.*, 1949, 71, 1384.

Cyclopentanone was condensed with diethyl homophthalate, affording the half-ester (X) which on alkaline hydrolysis yielded a mixture of α -cyclopentylidenehomophthalic acid and its anhydride. The structure of the anhydride was confirmed by analysis and by its hydrolysis to the acid. The position of the double bond in the dicarboxylic acid was confirmed by oxidation to cyclopentanone by cold dilute potassium permanganate. The UV spectrum of the compound exhibited end absorption only. Experiments on the cyclisation of the half-ester (X) led to the formation of the anhydride only; no other product could be isolated. The condensation of cycloheptanone with diethyl homophthalate afforded the half-ester (XI: R=Et) or its double-bond isomer. The related dicarboxylic acid could, however, be oxidised to cycloheptanone, indicating that the double bond is exo-cyclic. In this case also, no information could be obtained from UV spectrum as this compound also, showed end absorption. The half-ester on cyclisation gave the naphthalene derivative (XII: R=CO₂Et; R'=Ac) which could not be obtained in a crystalline condition. On alkaline hydrolysis, however, the naphthol (XII: R=CO₂Et; R'=H) was obtained in a pure condition (the ester group remaining unchanged during the reaction*). This phenol did not develop any coloration with ferric chloride.

α -Tetralone on the Stobbe condensation gave the expected half-ester (XIII: R=Et; R'=H) or its isomer which on hydrolysis furnished α -[1-(3,4-dihydronaphthyl)]homophthalic acid (XIII: R=R'=H). The ethylenic double bond in this compound appears to be situated in the alicyclic ring in conjugation with aromatic ring as it fails to yield any tetralone on oxidation. In the ultraviolet the compound absorbed maximally at 226 m μ (log ϵ , 3.89) and 262 m μ (log ϵ , 3.62); the latter absorption appears to corroborate the structure shown as both 3,4-dihydro-1-naphthylacetic acid and 1,2-dihydro-4-methylnaphthalene absorb at 262 m μ (log ϵ , 3.88 and 3.82 respectively)¹⁰.

In fact, regardless of whether the double bond is *exo*- or *endo*cyclic, cyclisation in either case should lead to the desired anthracene derivative through a common intermediate. Cyclisation of the half-ester with the aid of zinc chloride led to ester (XIV: R=CO₂Et; R'=Ac) which on hydrolysis gave the phenolic ester (XIV: R=CO₂Et; R'=H) in a crystalline condition. As before, the phenol did not respond to ferric reaction.

In an analogous manner, the pentacyclic compound (XV) was prepared from 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthren-1-one.

EXPERIMENTAL*

α-Cinnamylidenehomophthalic Acid.—A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (1.9 g.) and cinnamaldehyde (0.72 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium hydride (0.2 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml) with rigid exclusion of moisture when a slow reaction set in at the room temperature. The mixture was left overnight, decomposed with water, and the oily half-ester isolated from the alkaline solution. The half-ester was hydrolysed by boiling with a 10% NaOH solution (20 ml) and then acidified to give *α-cinnamylidenehomophthalic acid* (2.1 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in a yellowish prismatic mass, m.p. 228-30° (decomp.). (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.0. C₁₈H₁₄O₄ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8%).

Reduction.—The above acid (1.0 g.), dissolved in 10% NaOH solution (10 ml), was treated with an excess of sodium amalgam (100 g., 1%). Isolated as usual, *α*-(3-phenylpropyl)homophthalic acid (0.80 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in a colorless mass, m.p. 184°. The compound exhibited a deep red coloration with H₂SO₄ (conc.). (Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.6. C₁₈H₁₈O₄ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.0%). Cyclisation of the compound was attempted with hot polyphosphoric acid, sulphuric acid, and phosphorous oxychloride, but without success.

All m.p.s are uncorrected.

Condensation of Terephthalaldehyde with Diethyl Homophthalate

To a solution of sodium ethoxide (Na 0.2 g. and dry ethanol 15 ml) a mixture of diethyl homophthalate (0.95 g.) and terephthalaldehyde (0.53 g.) was added; the mixture was ~~reduced for 2~~ hours on the water bath, then cooled, diluted with water, and the unchanged substance extracted with ether. The aqueous layer containing the half-ester was boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with a 10% NaOH solution (15 ml). The mixture was then cooled and acidified with HCl when the tetracarboxylic acid (III: R=H) was obtained which crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid in cream-coloured plates (1.6 g.), m.p. 239-40° (the colour turning orange at 230° due to formation of the anhydride). (Found: C, 68.2; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 68.1; H, 3.9%).

The *anhydride* was obtained as bright orange crystals, m.p. 274-75° (decomp.) on treatment with acetic anhydride. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 3.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 74.0; H, 3.3%).

Reduction.—The foregoing acid (0.3 g.), dissolved in a solution of NaOH, was treated with sodium amalgam (40 g., 2%) and left for 24 hours. On acidification, a gummy mass was obtained which crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (0.17 g.), m.p. 192-93°. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 5.0. $C_{26}H_{22}O_8$ requires C, 67.5; H, 4.7%).

Cyclisation.—The above acid (0.6 g.) was finely powdered, heated, and stirred at 140° with polyphosphoric acid in an oil bath for 1½ hours. The temperature was raised to 175° which was maintained for a further period of $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After treatment with iced water, the solid was collected and washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution. The isocoumarin (VII) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in dirty brown needles, m.p. >310° (with slight sintering). (Found: C, 72.8; H, 4.3. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 73.2; H, 4.2%).

Condensation of Acetophenone with Diethyl Homophthalate

A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (3.8 g.) and freshly distilled acetophenone (1.3 g.) was added to sodium hydride (0.04 g.) in dry benzene and left overnight at the room temperature. Next day, the deep red solution was acidified with dilute acetic acid when a colorless organic layer separated. The benzene solution was extracted with several portions of sodium carbonate solution (5%) and the alkaline extracts were extracted with ether. Acidification of the extract precipitated the *half-ester* in the form of an oil which was isolated with ether. The compound solidified on keeping and it was crystallised from ethanol. *Ethyl α -o-carboxyphenyl- β -methyl- β -phenylacrylate* separated as colorless plates, yield 4.0 g., m.p. 150-51°. (Found: C, 73.4; H, 5.7. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 5.8%).

The above half-ester (3.5 g.) was heated on the water bath with a 10% NaOH solution (25 ml) for 2 hours and then filtered; the alkaline filtrate was acidified. The resulting yellowish mass of *α -o-carboxyphenyl- β -methyl- β -phenylacrylic acid* was crystallised from acetic acid as colorless prisms, yield 3.0 g., m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 4.9%).

This acid on reduction with sodium amalgam in the usual way furnished a quantitative yield of *α -o-carboxyphenyl- β -methyl- β -phenylpropionic acid* which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

2-o-Ethoxycarbonylphenyl-3-methylindenone.—The half-ester (VIII) (2.1 g.) was refluxed for 8 hours with a mixture of acetic anhydride (19 ml) and a 5% solution of zinc chloride in acetic acid (3.6 ml). The mixture was decomposed with excess of water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent the *indenone* was obtained as yellow prisms, yield 0.5 g., m.p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 5.6. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.1; H, 5.5%). The 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid in yellow prisms, m.p. 185-86°.

2-o-Ethoxycarbonylphenyl-3-methyl-6,7-benzo-1-indenone.—A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (4.5 g.) and 2-acetylnaphthalene (1.9 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium hydride (0.45 g.) in benzene (10 ml), cooled in ice water. The mixture was left at room temperature for 16 hours and then worked up in the usual way. Hydrolysis of the half-ester obtained gave α -o-carboxyphenyl- β -methyl- β -(2-naphthyl)acrylic acid which crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 204-11° (gas evolution). The half-ester (1.5 g.) was cyclised by gently refluxing with a mixture of acetic acid, acetic anhydride, and zinc chloride, as before, for 1½ hours. On working up, the *indenone* was obtained as a brown viscous mass which readily afforded a 2,4-DNP, readily crystallising from acetic acid in red prisms, m.p. 252° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{29}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.7%).

2-o-Ethoxycarbonylphenyl-3-methyl-4,5-benzo-1-indenone was similarly prepared from 1-acetylnaphthalene and obtained as a gum, affording a crystalline 2,4-DNP, m.p. 235-38°. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{29}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.7%).

α -Cyclopentylidenehomophthalic Acid

A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (4.1 g.) and cyclopentanone (1.1 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium hydride (0.5 g.) in dry benzene (20ml). The mixture was stirred occasionally and then left overnight. The deep dark red solution was treated with dilute acetic acid and the organic layer worked up as before to afford the half-ester as an oil (5.1 g.). On alkaline hydrolysis for 2 hours, the half-ester (4.0 g.) furnished *cyclopentylidenehomophthalic acid*, yield 0.35 g., m.p. 212-13° (from acetic acid). (Found: C, 68.4; H, 5.7. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.3; H, 5.7%).

The mother liquor, on concentration almost to dryness, gave a viscous liquid from which the *anhydride* was obtained as greyish plates, m.p. 124-25°, on crystallisation from ethanol. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.3%). The anhydride on hydrolysis affords the acid and the latter may be dehydrated with acetic anhydride to the anhydride.

Oxidation.—A solution of the anhydride or the acid (0.1 g.) was treated with a solution of $KMnO_4$ (0.13 g.) in water (6 ml) in presence of sodium carbonate solution (0.08 g. in 5 ml of water). After keeping for 2 hours at the room temperature, the mixture was distilled into a solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl (conc.). The precipitated hydrazone crystallised from ethanol in orange-red prisms, m.p. 156°, unchanged on admixture with an authentic specimen of the 2,4-DNP of cyclopentanone.

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α-Cycloheptenylhomophthalic Acid

A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (3.6 g.) and *cycloheptanone* (1.2 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium hydride (0.42 g.) in dry benzene (17 ml) at the room temperature and left overnight. Next day the reddish green fluorescent solution was worked up to afford *half-ester* (XI: R=Et) (2.8 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 117°. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.3%).

The ester (2.0 g.) on hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide on the water bath gave a quantitative yield of *α-cycloheptylidenehomophthalic acid*, m.p. 227°, from acetic acid. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6%).

Oxidation.—A solution of the acid (0.1 g.) in sodium carbonate solution (0.08 g. in 5 ml of water) was treated with a solution of $KMnO_4$ (0.13 g.) in water (6 ml). After leaving for 2 hours at the room temperature, the mixture was steam distilled and the distillate extracted with ether, washed with water, and dried. After removal of ether, the 2,4-DNP was prepared of the residue in the usual way. This crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 149°, unchanged on admixture with an authentic specimen of the 2,4-DNP of cycloheptanone.

Ethyl 4-Hydroxy-2,3-cycloheptanonaphthalene-1-carboxylate.—The foregoing half-ester (2.2 g.) was refluxed for 4 hours with acetic anhydride (12 ml) and acetic acid containing fused zinc chloride (0.1 g.) The product was treated with water and the resulting oil isolated with ether. The etheral solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and the resulting oil hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide solution (10%), filtered, and saturated with carbon dioxide when a solid mass separated. The *phenol* crystallised from ethanol in light yellow prisms (0.08 g.), m.p. 135-36°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 7.1%).

α-1-(3,4-Dihydronaphthyl)homophthalic Acid

The condensation of diethyl homophthalate (8.8 g.) with 1-tetralone (3.9 g.) in presence of sodium hydride (1.1 g.) was carried out as before and the resulting *half-ester* (10 g.) crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.9; H, 5.9%).

On hydrolysis with a 10% NaOH solution for 2 hours on the water bath the *dicarboxylic acid* was obtained in colorless plates, m.p. 145-46° (gas evolution). $\lambda_{max}^{1\%}$ 226 m μ (log ϵ , 3.89), 262 m μ (log ϵ , 3.62). (Found: C, 74.1; H, 5.2. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.2%).

Ethyl 10-Acetoxy-1,2-benzo-3,4-dihydroanthracene-9-carboxylate.—The above half-ester (2.5 g.), derived from tetralone, was refluxed for 5½ hours with acetic anhydride (12 ml) and acetic acid containing fused zinc chloride (0.1 g.). The mixture was decomposed cautiously with excess of water and then worked up in the usual manner. The ester was crystallised from ethanol in yellowish white prisms, yield 2.1 g., m.p. 163-64°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 5.6. $C_{23}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.6%).

The above compound (1.0 g.) on hydrolysis with 10% NaOH solution (30 ml) followed by saturation with CO_2 , afforded *ethyl-10-hydroxy-1,2-benzo-3,4-dihydroanthracene-9-carboxylate* (0.6 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in reddish prisms, m.p. 163-64°. (Found: C, 79.1; H, 5.5. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 79.2; H, 5.7%). The phenol does not give ferric reaction.

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Ethy 10-Acetoxy-(1,2-2,1)naphtho-3,4-dihydroanthracene-9-carboxylate.—To a suspension of sodium hydride (0.12 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml) were added a mixture of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthren-1-one (0.59 g.) and diethyl homophthalate (1.1 g.) and a drop of ethanol at the room temperature; the mixture was left for 16 hours. The whole mass was then acidified with acetic acid and the organic layer worked up to give the half-ester (0.8 g.) as an oil which was cyclised with acetic anhydride (10 ml), acetic acid (10 ml) and zinc chloride (0.05 g.) by heating under reflux for 2 hours. After decomposition with water, the mass was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried, and the ether removed. The ester crystallised from methanol in yellowish prisms, m.p. 160-61°. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 5.7. $C_{27}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 79.0; H, 5.4%).

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